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2ND POLICY BRIEF

STRENGTHENING CLIMATE SCIENCE AND MODELLING COMMUNITIES THROUGH HACKATHONS: LESSONS FROM THE NEXTGEMS PROJECT

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SUMMARY

km-scale Earth-system models

The nextGEMS project has pioneered the first multi-decadal km-scale Earth System Models (ESMs) simulations. NextGEMS achieved this milestone in the timespan of 3,5 years through an innovative approach to research project management, moving away from traditional meetings to engaging project partners and interested parties through a series of interdisciplinary hackathons. Far from being short-lived coding sprints—the traditional understanding of hackathons—, these events created fertile ground for knowledge exchange between scientists at different career stages, deepened collaboration between developers and model users, and supported the emergence of a more integrated modelling community. This policy brief distils key lessons from these hackathons and outlines recommendations for research projects, funders, and technical support providers aiming to accelerate scientific collaboration and innovation in Earth system modelling.

KEY MESSAGES

- Hackathons foster knowledge exchange across career-stages and disciplines, helping bridge the gap between scientific insight and technical implementation.
- Technical support teams gain real-time insights into user needs, enabling more effective, user-centred development of tools and platforms, enhancing the usability of climate modelling outputs .
- Hackathons cultivate lasting professional networks and shared ownership over models and outputs, strengthening the research community.
- Recurring, well-structured events provide rhythm and motivation, aligning collaborative work cycles across institutions, and supporting a robust and long-lasting legacy of projects.
- This participatory model can be replicated in other research contexts to enhance interdisciplinary collaboration and knowledge co-production.
- Overall, building integrated climate science and modelling communities requires more than code and data. It demands spaces for human interaction, where skills are exchanged, infrastructures are shaped together, and trust is built across disciplines and career stages. For the future of km-scale Earth system modelling, such community-driven approaches are essential.

CONTEXT: WHY IT MATTERS?

Developing km-scale Earth system models is a formidable challenge. These models promise improved representation of extreme weather events, local climate phenomena, and feedback mechanisms. Yet the path from code to actionable knowledge is long, and it requires not just technical innovation but also human collaboration.

Traditional project structures often fall short in enabling deep, iterative, interdisciplinary work that km-scale modelling demands. The nextGEMS project and its emphasis on engaging its community through periodic hackathons offered a new format: a recurring space for scientists, coders, modelers, and knowledge co-production experts, to collaborate intensively, learn from one another, and shape shared infrastructure in real time.

Figure, see references

LESSONS LEARNT

1 Intergenerational learning in action. Hackathons brought together early-career researchers fluent in new coding tools and senior scientists with deep domain expertise. Rather than top-down training, learning flowed thus in multiple directions. Juniors helped by requesting and reframing workflows and brought motivation for exploring new research questions, and seniors contextualized the knowledge that emerged from new studies.

2 Technical development grounded in user needs. A core achievement of the hackathons was creating feedback loops between users and technical support staff. This was especially relevant because the project demanded participants to handle vast amounts of simulation data. Infrastructure teams adapted platforms like EasyGEMS, available online, based on observed barriers rather than assumed ones. This continuous dialogue allowed to develop improved data access and management workflows, better preprocessing tools, and overall improved the speed at which scientists could start using and testing the new simulations that came at each hackathon cycle.

3 Building networks and shared ownership. Projects need joint ownership to be successful, and continued interactions through hackathons allowed project participants to be more attached to and feel responsible for the achievement of the project main goals. Beyond this impressive output, the hackathons served also as incubators for long-term collaboration. Participants reported initiating joint publications, continued use of shared tools after the hackathons, and follow-up meetings with peers across institutions. Social activities, shared meals, and structured group work contributed to joint project endeavour.

WHAT MADE THE HACKATHONS WORK?

SEVERAL DESIGN FEATURES CONTRIBUTED TO THE SUCCESS

Regular cadence

events were spaced 6–9 months apart and were tied to data releases.

Onboarding

preparatory materials and meetings prior to the hackathons helped level the field for newcomers.

Diversity of roles

participation from model developers, technical staff, scientist from all the required expertise of the climate system, and co-production experts ensured rich collaboration.

Embedded support

technical teams worked alongside researchers. NextGEMS opted for not distributing the technical experts in groups, rather, they were available to address requests from users.

Social engineering design

Shared spaces, ice-breaking activities, and joint scientific sessions at the end of the day, further integrated the community.

[See the blogpost: "The Stockholm hackathon ended with an integrated Climate Science community". April 2025.](#)

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

for research funders

- Recognize collaborative events like hackathons as essential investments in scientific development, especially for earth system modelling. Allocate dedicated funding for co-productive formats that support peer learning, open and interactive development, and interdisciplinarity, including support for participants from underrepresented regions.
- Promote intergenerational and institutional diversity by integrating mentoring, career-stage bridging, and inclusive participation into funding criteria. Incentivize partnerships with underrepresented institutions and researchers.

for research project coordinators

- Embed hackathons as core project milestones, replacing or complementing traditional meetings. Use them to accelerate development cycles, test outputs at an early stage, and reinforce shared ownership of tasks between model developers, users, and infrastructure teams.
- Design projects to foster interdisciplinary skills and career development, particularly for early-career researchers. Provide structured opportunities for peer exchange, mentoring, and hands-on problem-solving.

for technical teams

- Integrate technical support staff directly into user environments during collaborative events. This enables rapid response to user needs and speeds up tool development iteration based on real-world better tailored workflows.
- Prioritize user-centred design by embedding continuous feedback mechanisms, ensuring infrastructure evolves alongside user capabilities and demands.

About the Project

nextGEMS is a collaborative European project. Funded by the EU's Horizon 2020 programme, it will tap expertise from fourteen European Nations to develop two next generation (storm-resolving) Earth-system Models. Through breakthroughs in simulation realism, these models will allow us to understand and reliably quantify how the climate will change on a global and regional scale, and how the weather, including its extreme events, will look like in the future.

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Figure in page X: Eyring, V., Gentine, P., Camps-Valls, G., Lawrence, D. M., & Reichstein, M. (2024). AI-empowered next-generation multiscale climate modelling for mitigation and adaptation. *Nature Geoscience*, 17(10), 963-971.

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